

Most People Are Morally Obligated to Stop “Working”

Abstract

Throughout history, the word "work" referred primarily to "activity necessary for survival", such as farming and building shelter. Another definition of the word "work" is "created intellectual artifact", such as works of art or major works in philosophy. Today, most "work" in the so-called developed world clearly fulfills neither definition, so what definition does it fulfill? According to David Graeber (2018), the answer is *Bullshit Jobs*, as his eponymous book explains. This short essay can be considered a "spiritual successor" to his (2013) initial article called "On the Phenomenon of Bullshit Jobs: A Work Rant". While the author himself referred to the text as a "rant", that was clearly meant modestly, as "to rant" usually means "to speak or write in an angry or emotionally charged manner", which describes neither that text nor this one. This one, however, will focus more on the moral aspect of the unnecessary nature of most modern so-called jobs.

Keywords: philosophy of work, labor ethics, bullshit jobs, misallocation of labor, social philosophy, work and meaning, escapism

Objective

"The moral and spiritual damage that comes from this situation is profound. It is a scar across our collective soul." This statement appears in the introduction of his essay, but is not meaningfully expanded neither in the essay nor in the book. Before the ethics can be explained, however, the question of what counts as necessary work must be answered. Indeed, Graeber describes how his job itself, as an anthropologist, would be considered "bullshit" by many people. The way he chose to distinguish between jobs is by asking this question: "What would happen were this entire class of people to simply disappear?" Were agricultural workers to vanish, humanity would quickly starve. Were musicians to vanish, one aspect of humanity would end. Were lobbyists, actuaries, telemarketers, legal consultants and so on to vanish, many believe humanity would in fact improve. As such, there are clearly at least 3 types of bullshit jobs:

- No bullshit: jobs technically necessary for survival
- Some bullshit: jobs not technically necessary but nice to have
- Full bullshit: jobs useless or even harmful to society

Ultimately, to properly answer what counts as necessary, one must have an objective. Without an objective, anything and everything could count as "bullshit". However, humanity has not agreed what its objective is. What tends to be called "bullshit" is simply anything that is not necessary for survival. Yet, if humanity's objective were simply to survive, then it is not doing a good job anyway. Firstly, it has been building weapons of mass destruction, such as nuclear bombs and artificial viruses (for example Wei et al., 2024). Secondly, there are, for instance, damocloids (Jewitt, 2005), poorly understood space objects that are currently almost impossible to detect and could destroy humanity, like the dinosaurs, at any time. While they are so busy "working", most people do not seem to realize that it is entirely possible for humanity to end at any time, either through its own whims or the whims of the universe. If they were not so busy "working", they might have actually had time to address real problems.

Other concepts people tend to invoke when asked about the purpose of their lives, are "love", "peace" and "happiness", and clearly humanity is failing at those as well. The more or less implicit purpose of society, of humanity, is the alleviation of its suffering. If that is the objective of society, then why is that not the objective of modern jobs? And if that is not the objective of society, then what is it?... This text will simply presuppose that the objective is "a better world" defined as a world in which people are as safe and free as possible because, again, without an objective, there can be no discussion on necessity, ethics, or indeed anything at all.

Necessary

By that standard, what jobs would be considered necessary? Governments do not agree exactly on the category of essential jobs, so let us try:

- water: water treatment workers
- food: agricultural workers

- basic logistics: transportation workers
- shelter: builders and architects
- healthcare: nurses and doctors
- energy: energy production workers

These jobs are the only jobs technically necessary for society to exist. Indeed, one could even make an argument that healthcare and energy are not technically necessary, but that would only make sense if the goal is purely the survival of the species. If the goal is safety and freedom, then of course they are essential. Yet, humanity is failing at these as well:

- The United Nations [UN] discovered that nearly 6 billion will suffer from clean water scarcity by 2050 (Boretti & Rosa, 2019). According to the same report, approximately half the world's population already suffers from water scarcity today.
- Researchers have discovered an alarming decline of nutritional quality in food due to modern farming practices, and described it as "The Biggest Challenge for Future Generations' Health" (Bhardwaj et al., 2024; Yilmaz & Yilmaz, 2025).
- Shelters are in fact possible for everyone.

Of course, this is not even to mention the environmental collapse, that 99% of people already live with unsafe levels of air pollution according to the World Health Organization [WHO] (2024), and that 7 out of 9 planetary boundaries of Earth's ecosystem have been breached (Planetary Boundaries Science [PBScience], 2025), for example. One might think this is new information. No, only the titles have become more and more desperate as they have been ignored. This information has been known for decades.

Escapism

If you assume humanity cares about survival, it does not make sense. If you assume humanity cares about happiness, it does not make sense. If you understand humanity cares about distraction, then it makes perfect sense. The previous statement that if people "were not so busy "working", they might have actually had time to address real problems", might have

seemed sarcastic or condescending, but it was in fact simply accurate. Graeber himself wrote, for example:

- "Yet it is the peculiar genius of our society that its rulers have figured out a way (...) to ensure that rage is directed precisely against those who actually do get to do meaningful work."
- "Clearly, the system was never consciously designed. It emerged from almost a century of trial and error."

Perhaps he was not being equally literal everywhere, but the point is that most people seem to simultaneously believe the "ruling class" is made up of both the smartest and dumbest people in the world. When the system is stable, they are "brilliant manipulators". When the system is failing, they are "incompetent idiots". Moreover, he states: "If someone had designed a work regime perfectly suited to maintaining the power of finance capital, it's hard to see how they could have done a better job." Really? I am inclined to think literally anything else would have worked better for everyone, including the "financial class". Indeed, most people seem to believe that they are working for the sake of the "elites". Yes, I am sure that the "elites" can feel their power growing with every flipped fast food burger and every stamped permit...

So if modern "work" does not even help the "elite", then what is its point?... Graeber described this as "some strange alchemy no one can quite explain". What do people call an activity of which purpose is to distract oneself from reality? Escapism. What is the definition of modern "work"? Escapism: Modern "work" is a socially celebrated way to feel good about oneself. Modern inessential "jobs", especially in the "developed world", exist exclusively for the sake of distracting oneself from the fact that humanity is fundamentally failing at every possible level. As such, if you participate in such "work", you are morally obligated to stop and consider what you are doing.

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